

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 17

◆ South Africa

Low oxygen, rock lobster strandings and PSP

The latter months of the summer of 1997 were characterised by a massive bloom of the dinoflagellate *Ceratium furca* on the West Coast of South Africa. Inshore accumulations of the bloom were first observed in January and by April cell concentrations, in some instances, exceeded 20 million cells l⁻¹. Although

dominated by the dinoflagellate *Ceratium furca* both *Alexandrium catenella* and *Dinophysis acuminata*, responsible for Paralytic and Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning respectively, were present as minor components of the bloom. Ex-

(Cont'd on p. 3)

◆ India

Another outbreak of PSP in India

An outbreak of paralytic shellfish poisoning occurred in three villages, Vizhinjam, Poovar, and Karumkulum near Thiruvananthapuram, the capital of Kerala State in the south west coast of India. Seven persons died and over 500 people were hospitalised following consumption of mussels, *Perna indica* during the first week of September, 1997. The affected persons showed typical clinical symptoms such as tingling sensation in the facial area, numbness of limbs, vomiting etc. The UNESCO Mircen for Marine Biotechnology, Dept. of Fishery Microbiology, College of Fisheries, Mangalore carried out analysis of water and shellfish samples. The mussels had very high levels of PSP (levels exceeding 10,000 Mouse Units/100g). At the time of the outbreak, water had high counts of cyanobacteria.

While the exact source of the toxin has not yet been identified, this outbreak has created a scare among fish consumers in the Kerala State. The sale of shellfish has been banned and this is said to have rendered about 1000 families jobless. The toxin levels are being monitored by the College of Fisheries, Mangalore. The Vizhinjam Centre of Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute

(CMFRI) has been providing the samples at regular intervals for the analysis. During the four weeks of monitoring the level of toxins in shellfish has dropped to less than 500 MU, but it is still not safe for human consumption. Further studies on the toxin and dinoflagellates in the region are under way. This is the second confirmed outbreak of PSP in India. The earlier outbreak was in the northern part of Kerala State, in a place called Kumble about 50 km South of Mangalore (Karunasagar et al., Curr. Sci; 53, 247, 1984). Recent observation of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in the waters close to this area (Godhe et al. HAB News 15, 1; 1996) and observation of cysts of toxic dinoflagellates in the sediment close to this area (Godhe et al., Abst. VIII International Conf. Harmful Algae, Vigo 1997, p88) suggest that this area is prone to shellfish intoxication and this calls for regular monitoring in this coast for toxins, dinoflagellates and cysts.

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◆ New Zealand

Gymnodinium sp. linked to fish kills

In the Southern Hemisphere, as seasonal warming progressed in the 1997-98 period, several major events occurred in the New Zealand region. In early January 1998 mass mortalities of sea lion pups were reported in the Auckland Islands area to the south of South Island (Fig. 1). Also reported from mid-January to early February, were sporadic fish kills along the Kaikoura and Wairarapa coasts on the central east coast of New Zealand, and shellfish toxicity at Great Barrier Island on the northeast coast of North Island.

Off the Wairarapa coast tuna, striped marlin, broad bill swordfish, sea urchins, starfish, and abalone were reported killed along the coastline between Castle Point and Palliser Bay. In early February 1998 there were reports of human respiratory symptoms in several areas off the coast. A group of school children, residents, swimmers, and beachgoers at Riversdale, Castle Point and Mataikona, complained of a dry cough, sore throats, burning nasal passages, and eye and skin irritations. From late January to early February in the region, nearly 200 people were reported to have suffered from these symptoms. Most people recovered on leaving the affected area and no lasting effect was noted. At the time, a non-thecate dinoflagellate, *Gymnodinium* cf. *mikimotoi* was identified by the National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research (NIWA) from water samples in the region. The presence of these respiratory symptoms in humans coincided with the monospecific build-up of *G. cf. mikimotoi* (up to 1.17×10^5 cells l⁻¹) in the same areas.

In mid-February, "aerosol" effects on humans were reported in several coastal areas in Hawke Bay. At the time reasonably high concentrations of *G. cf. miki-*

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◆ USA ECOHAB

Major study on *Alexandrium*

Harmful algal blooms, commonly called "red tides" or HABs, are a serious economic and public health problem throughout the world. In the U.S., the most serious HAB problem is paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP), a potentially fatal neurological disorder caused by human ingestion of shellfish that accumulate toxins as they feed on dinoflagellates of the genus *Alexandrium*. These organisms cause human illness and death due to PSP, repeated shellfish harvest quarantines, and the mortality of fish and marine mammals. This phenomenon, which affects thousands of miles of U.S. coastline and numerous fisheries resources, has expanded dramatically in the last two decades, especially in the Gulf of Maine. As part of the Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (ECOHAB) research program, scientists are embarking on a six-year study that will address several fundamental issues regarding *Alexandrium* blooms in the Gulf of Maine "The Ecology and Oceanography of Toxic *Alexandrium* Blooms in the Gulf of Maine; ECOHAB-GOM": 1) the source of the *Alexandrium* cells that appear in the fresh water plumes in the western Maine coastal current (WMCC); 2) *Alexandrium* cell distribution and dynamics in the eastern Maine coastal current (EMCC), and 3) linkag-

es among blooms in the WMCC, the EMCC and on Georges Bank. Utilizing a combination of numerical modeling, hydrographic, chemical, and biological measurements, moored and drifting current measurements, and satellite imagery, ECOHAB-GOM will characterize the structure, variability and autecology of the major *Alexandrium* habitats in the Gulf of Maine.

In the western Gulf, *Alexandrium* blooms and patterns of PSP have been linked to a coastal current or plume of low salinity river outflow (the WMCC). One major project goal is to investigate the area implicated as the major "source region" for the toxic cells that populate that coastal current. ECOHAB-GOM will elucidate the biological, chemical, and physical processes that control bloom initiation and development, the delivery of cells from that source region into the WMCC, and the manner in which late-season, localized blooms are retained there to re-seed future blooms with cysts. The second major set of objectives is to characterize the linkage between toxic blooms and the EMCC, to investigate the role of tidal mixing, frontal systems, and upwelling/ downwelling in *Alexandrium* dynamics, and to define the linkage between EMCC *Alexandrium* populations and those in both the WMCC (downstream) and the

Bay of Fundy (upstream). Another project element will examine toxicity on Georges Bank, a rich shellfish resource that is a downstream delivery site for toxic cells from both coastal currents.

A unique set of "process" studies will focus on discrete blooms or patches of cells and quantify such parameters as *in situ* growth rates and grazing losses of *Alexandrium*, the nutritional physiology, vertical migration behavior and transport of this species, the partitioning of toxins within the food web, and the extent to which mixotrophy supplements photosynthesis. A hierarchy of coupled physical-biological models will be used together with ECOHAB-GOM data for investigation of: 1) detailed structure within each habitat; 2) interconnections among habitats; and 3) the role of the large Gulf-scale circulation in the long-term maintenance of *Alexandrium* populations in the region. Advances in our understanding of the underlying mechanisms controlling the population dynamics of *Alexandrium* will be distilled into simple predictive models of PSP toxicity which can be driven by a relatively small number of observable parameters. ECOHAB-GOM is thus a combined modeling/observational program, utilizing the most current and innovative technologies in an approach commensurate with the multiple scales and oceanographic complexity of PSP phenomena in the Gulf of Maine.

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◆ Spain

Iberoamerican cooperation on HAB Training

The IOC, the Institute for Iberoamerican Cooperation (ICI), and the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) organized from 29 June to 16 July 1997 a broad course on toxic phytoplankton with special emphasis on the detection and quantification of marine phycotoxins (bioassays, *in vivo* and *in vitro*, chemical, immuno-enzymatic and biochemical techniques) implemented in research and monitoring programmes.

Participants were from Argentina, Brasil, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Guatemala, Mexico, Peru and Madagascar. In addition to staff from the Instituto Español de Oceanografía, The Laboratorio de Sanidad Exterior (European Commu-

nity Reference Laboratory on Marine Biotoxins), and Conselleria de Pesca, Marisqueo e Acuicultura (Xunta de Galicia), teaching was complemented by invited speakers from the Università di Trieste (Italy), Tohoku University (Japan), Osaka Prefectural Institute of Public Health (Japan) and Iatron Laboratories (Japan). To complement the training, participants were also invited to attend the VIII International Conference on Harmful Algae that preceded the course. Technical assistance for the course was provided by Gilson-Pacisa (Madrid, Spain) and Upstate Biotechnology Research (Lake Placid, USA)

Since 1996, annual courses on toxic

phytoplankton have been held at the IEO, Vigo. These courses are given in Spanish. Priority is given to applicants with responsibilities for research, monitoring, toxin control and other management tasks. Although most students have basic knowledge of English, classes in Spanish facilitate communication and favour scientific exchange, especially during a 15-20 day course.

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haustion of nutrients and eventual decay of the bloom inshore lead to oxygen depletion throughout the water column. As a consequence a stranding of more than 1500 tons of the rock lobster, *Jasus lalandii*, took place in April at Elands Bay on the West Coast, as lobsters concentrated in the shallow surf zone in an attempt to escape bottom oxygen concentrations which declined to below detectable limits (Figure). During the ensuing weeks, several further strandings were observed, all south of Elands Bay, and the total loss was eventually estimated to be 2000 tons of lobster. These strandings are the largest ever recorded and have raised concern about the future of stocks in this area. To provide perspective, the total allowable catch for the entire coastline is currently 1700 tons. Of particular concern was that almost all of the stranded animals were under the legal size limit.

Standings of rock lobster as a consequence of low oxygen are common on the West Coast and are most frequent in the vicinity of Elands Bay, one of the richer lobster grounds. This stranding was, however, unprecedented in terms of the magnitude of the losses which were estimated at 50 million US\$. The timing, over a weekend, and magnitude of the stranding, combined with inadequate control and considerable confusion on whether lobsters could be harvested by the public, resulted in a chaotic situation which secured considerable media attention. Although some 200 tons of beached lobsters were saved through the co-operative efforts of Sea Fisheries, the Industry, the Police and the Defence Force, most of the animals that came ashore died before

they could be rescued and were buried on the beach. Many were harvested and sold illegally and about 300 tons were ground up and turned into fish meal or tailed and packed for commercial retail. The authorities were opposed to any concessions allowing people to gather the lobsters for sale, not only because this would have contravened the law and established policy, but because of the danger of food poisoning arising from consumption of spoiled lobsters.

Because rock lobster are relatively slow growing and long-lived, the fishery in this region is likely to be slow in recovery, unless extensive migration occurs into the region. Trap and dive surveys conducted soon after the major stranding indicated dramatic reductions in the number of lobsters on the conventional fishing grounds in the Elands Bay region. Of the initial strandings of lobsters, 60-70% consisted of females, which normally comprise only 45 % of the total lobster population. This is thought to have occurred because females are typically restricted to shallower waters. The lobster population remaining in the area now appears to have a disproportionately large fraction of male lobsters – in recent trap samples less than 3% of the captured lobsters were female.

The economic implication of this catastrophe for those living in the Elands Bay region is uncertain. The rock lobster fishery forms the mainstay of the fishing industry in this area which in turn forms an indispensable part of the economic sector of the region. Local fishermen claim that the money they earn during the rock lobster season sees them through the remaining half of the year, when they are either unemployed or

work part-time as potato diggers. The rock lobster industry is already beleaguered by slow lobster growth rates that have led to declining total allowable catches – these strandings are likely to contribute seriously to the adversity of the fishing community.

Although *A. catenella* generally comprised a small component of the blooms on the West Coast it was present in sufficiently high concentrations to render shellfish toxic and in March Sea Fisheries placed a ban on the collection of wild shellfish as PSP toxins exceeded the harvestable limit of 80 µg 100g⁻¹ mussel tissue. Despite this banning several incidents of PSP were reported during April and May. On the 30 April a woman died after she and her partner had eaten a meal of white mussels, *Donax serra* and on the 9 May a second woman died from PSP after a meal of black mussels, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. Toxin concentrations from mussel samples collected on the West Coast varied considerably with a highest concentration of 2600 µg toxin 100g⁻¹ mussel tissue being recorded during May. On the 13 May four Taiwanese sailors were admitted to hospital following a meal of both raw and cooked mussels. On admittance the condition of all the men was described as ataxic, but one man was in a critical condition in that he was breathing intermittently and was placed on an artificial ventilator. This was the first case in South Africa in which a patient suffering from PSP has been recovered in this way. These represent the first fatalities on the South African coast as a consequence of PSP since 1958. The ban on the collection of shellfish was only lifted in August, 5 months after the initial banning. The above cases of PSP highlight the difficulties of communicating a restriction on the collection of shellfish in a country in which many languages are spoken and in which there is a high level of illiteracy. The need to police and enforce these bannings was therefore emphasized.

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(Cont'd from p. 1 "Gymnodinium sp. linked to fish kills")

motoi were also recorded by Cawthron Institute from water samples in the Hawke Bay area. At this point in March further outbreaks of respiratory illness were reported in the Wellington Harbour, and again the culprit is suggested to be *G. cf. mikimotoi*.

This is the first time that a build-up of *G. cf. mikimotoi* has been recorded off the east coast of North Island, and the first time that the presence of this species has been implicated in outbreaks of respiratory symptoms in New Zealand. Previously, an aerosol episode on humans on the northeast coast of North Island, New Zealand, was related to a different, but closely related species, *G. cf. breve* [1]. In South Africa in the summer of 1995-96, the presence of *G. cf. mikimotoi* was also linked to an aerosol effect on humans, where beachgoers and seaside residents were reported to have suffered from respiratory symptoms [2].

To date, tests on the cause of the sea lion deaths are not conclusive and are on-going. However, samples collected from Kaikoura by scientists at NIWA were analysed and tested positive for algal toxin by the Environmental Science Research (ESR). Sea urchins and starfish tested were shown to contain a microalgal toxin that is similar to gymnodimine. Gymnodimine has previously been established as being produced by *G. cf. mikimotoi* [3]. The detection of this lipid-soluble toxin suggests that this dinoflagellate species might also be present off Kaikoura at the time of fish

Fig. 1. Sampling locations around New Zealand between mid-January and early February 1998.

Fig. 2. Sea surface temperature (SST) anomaly in the New Zealand region during February 1998 (compared to the base period 1993 to 1997 inclusive). The contour interval is 0.5°C.

kills. No toxin, however, was detected in the guts of dead abalone or in striped marlin from the Wairarapa coast, and at this point the cause of death for both these species remains a mystery.

During the summer of 1997-98 *G. cf. mikimotoi* was a very widespread species on the east coast of New Zealand. Over this period large scale changes in oceanographic conditions in the region have been observed, and the widespread occurrence of this species has been suggested to be downstream effect of weather changes associated with the *El Nino* pattern.

High spatial resolution (1 km) sea surface temperature (SST) analyses derived from locally received NOAA Advanced Very High Resolution (AVHRR) data reveal that in January 1998 SST reversed the cooling effects of *El Nino* as experienced in the spring months (September to December 1997)

around the entire New Zealand coastal area. In Hawke Bay the anomaly changed from approx. -1°C in December to +1°C in January. A similar change occurred along the south Wairarapa coast. During February this warming increased still further with the SST anomaly reaching +2.5°C (Fig. 2). This strong positive anomaly is opposite to what was expected. Past *El Nino*'s have been accompanied by a cold anomaly (of the order of 1°C) in the New Zealand region.

Results from a research voyage off the east coast of North Island on NIWA's research vessel *Tangaroa* in the same period have shown that warmer subtropical water was found further to the south than usual, associated with strong southward current direction. This is consistent with observations of the SST from the AVHRR satellite images taken between mid January to mid February

1998. During this period the warming of nearshore waters by intrusions of warm oceanic waters, and the entrainment of nutrient-rich waters by upwelling have also been observed at several locations along the east coast. Research into the cause of these patterns and their relationship with the presence of toxic algae, is on-going.

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◆ France

New observations of raphidophyceae

During a routine sampling program on the impact of thermal perturbation from the Penly nuclear power plant in the western Channel (50° 00' N; 01° 11' E), conducted on 10 April 1996, significant numbers of *Chattonella*-like cells were observed for the first time in the coastal waters of northern France [1]. The phytoplankton community ($1:10^6$ cells l^{-1}) was dominated by the diatoms *Asterionella glacialis* and *Rhizosolenia delicatula* ($8:10^5$ cells l^{-1} and 1.10 cells l^{-1} respectively). Dinoflagellates (including *Scrippsiella trochoidea* and *Gymnodinium* sp.) were recorded at low densities ($3:10^3$ cells l^{-1}). Among nanoflagellates, presence of the cryptophyte *Plagioselmis* sp. was noted, while the silicoflagellate *Dictyocha speculum* reached concentrations of $1.5 \cdot 10^4$ cells l^{-1} .

Water temperature and salinity during the study were $8.7 \pm 1.5^\circ C$ and 34.1 ± 0.1 respectively, corresponding to the typical spring conditions for the area. Chlorophyll *a* concentration was $7.54 \pm 3.99 \mu g l^{-1}$, and nutrient concentrations were measured as: nitrate + nitrite ($13.77 \pm 0.67 \mu M$), ammonia ($0.14 \pm 0.09 \mu M$), phosphate ($0.51 \pm 0.05 \mu M$) and silicate ($2.07 \pm 0.71 \mu M$).

Counts of cells in Lugol-fixed samples, using an inverted microscope, indicated *Chattonella* abundance of $1.7 \cdot 10^4$ cells per litre. The cells were intact and well preserved except for loss of flagella (Fig. A), although some cells did show remnants of subapical flagella. No other raphidophycean-like cells were present in the sample, and since the be-

ginning of the survey of coastal waters around French power plants in 1976, raphidophytes in general had never been observed.

Living material is usually a requisite for reliable identification of raphidophytes, but the general aspect of the cell, the absence of a cell wall and the abundant peripherally located chloroplasts strongly indicate a raphidophycean species. Confusion with globular, fragile, uniflagellate naked stages of *Dictyocha* is unlikely, particularly as cells of this silicoflagellate were at the armoured stage at the time of sampling.

The cells of this raphidophyte are clearly distinct in shape and organization from another raphidophycean known to bloom in French coastal waters, *Heterosigma akashiwo* [2,3], illustrated at the comparable magnification in Figure B (from Lugol-fixed cultured material). Sporadic appearances of a third raphidophyte have also been previously reported in France, *Fibrocapsa japonica* [4, 3], but presence of rod-shaped, posteriorly located mucocysts which are ejected as long threads in dying cells (Fig. C) clearly distinguish this species from the genus *Chattonella* as a whole.

The general shape of the cells, the absence of mucocysts and the small size of this *Chattonella* (mean length 25 μm ; mean width 12 μm) indicate that these could be *C. minima*, one of the smallest species of the genus and only known thus far from Japan [5]. The cells observed here were somewhat smaller than the dimensions given for the Japanese isolates (20-45 μm long, 20-30 μm wide). *C. minima* is sometimes considered to be an ecotype of *C. marina*, an ichthyotoxic species recently recorded, along with *C. antiqua*, in Dutch coastal waters [6].

In order to confirm the identity of *C. minima*, live samples taken from the same period (16 April 1997) the following year. No raphidophyceans were found, while the general pattern of the phytoplankton community was very different from 1996, with total number of cells reduced by half ($5:10^5$ cells l^{-1}) in which *Rhizosolenia delicatula* and *Chaetoceros curvisetum* were dominant ($3:10^5$ and $6:10^4$ cells l^{-1} respectively). Abundant colonies of *Phaeocystis glo-*

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Identification Service

The IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen, and the Asian Natural Environmental Science Center offers an identification service. If you have problems with identification of harmful algal species, the Centres may assist you. You should send samples to one of the two addresses given below. It should be noted that this assistance is not given for routine identification/monitoring of samples, but applies to particular difficult species, or to

species that require special techniques e.g. electron microscopy, for identification.

IOC Science and Communication
Centre on Harmful Algae,
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Asian Environmental Science Center,
The University of Tokyo,
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Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113,
Japan.

bosa and *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp, not recorded the previous year, were also observed. Changes in temperature ($10.7 \pm 0.9^\circ \text{C}$) and in nutrient concentration ($6.54 \pm 0.94 \mu\text{M}$ nitrite + nitrate) could explain the absence of *C. minima* in 1997.

Chattonella species in general have so far never been observed by the phytoplankton monitoring network REPHY of IFREMER. *C. subsalsa* [5], a distinctive brackish organism from saline, eutrophic canals in southern France, is the only other recorded species of the genus in this country and it is known so far from its type locality only [7].

Of the 4 raphidophytes reported in France, only *Heterosigma akashiwo*, which is widely distributed along the French coasts, has been associated with fish kills, in 1994 [2]. Due to the toxic potential of most marine raphidophycan species, further problems related to their blooms might be expected in the future.

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Figs. (A) *Chattonella cf. minima* from Penly, Lugol-fixed. (B) *Heterosigma akashiwo* culture (RAP-1, Caen Culture Collection), Lugol-fixed cell. (C) *Fibrocapsa japonica* showing posterior ejected mucocysts, wild material from Calvados, Normandy (courtesy of J. Fresnel, Caen). Pictures taken with Nomarski interference contrast, (A) (B) obj. x 100 and (C) obj. x 40.

(A)

(B)

(C)

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◆ France

Recurrent observations of a *Gymnodinium breve*-like species

Gymnodinium breve or *Gymnodinium breve*-like cells [1] have been observed every year since 1994, along the western Brittany coast (French Atlantic coast). This species is observed usually from July to September with occasional observations in May 1995 and October 1997. In any case, cells counts from Ushant Island to Concarneau never exceeded 1500 cells l⁻¹ and no toxic event was reported.

Some morphological features were conserved *i.e.* peripheral chloroplasts, the round nucleus located in the posterior or left quadrant (Fig.1) and the dorso-ventral flattening. However, considerable variations in other characteristics of cell morphology were noted. The apex shape varied greatly from a pointed process to a prominent overhanging carina. Cell dimensions varied from 20 to 55 µm in width and from 15 to 30 µm in length. Nevertheless, it seems there is only one species and the different morphotypes have been counted together.

The species was not further identified because light microscopy doesn't allow a more detailed morphological analysis which should include the length of the sulcal intrusion onto the epicone and the length of the apical groove. Moreover, scanning electronic microscopy was not used because of the low concentrations in field samples and the lack of cultures.

Due to the toxicity observed along

USA East coast, this species is now monitored by the French monitoring network (REPHY). Since a similar species has also been reported in Galician waters [2], observations should be compared along the West and East Atlantic coast, in order to decide on the name species and its possible toxicity.

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Fig. 1: Light micrograph (x 1000) of the *Gymnodinium breve*-like species from Concarneau Bay.

◆ ICES-IOC

A Global Survey on harmful algal events

The ICES-IOC Working Group on the Dynamics of Harmful Algal Blooms is presently carrying out a survey to acquire information about the oceanographic aspects of harmful algal events around the world.

The results will be collated in order to formulate a basic description of the occurrence and time development of harmful algae in different locations. By documenting the similarities and differences between occurrences for the same species, the important features of the physi-

ology and environment can be identified. This information will be returned to the participants. We hope that global coverage can be achieved. The survey and its questionnaire is by no means complete. Everybody who feel that critical questions are missing, are welcome to identify them. A classification of the different types of events and scenarios would help greatly in the design of a science agenda for a potential international program on HABs. Broad representation across all harmful species is desirable in order to

discover the processes that extend across species boundaries.

The questionnaire is available at <http://www.unesco.org/ioc/oslr/survey.htm>
Your reply will be highly appreciated.

The questionnaire can also be requested by mail to P. Gentien.

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◆ Netherlands – Germany

Fibrocapsa japonica and *Heterosigma akashiwo*:
new observations

Since the early 1990s, potentially ichthyotoxic raphidophyte species like *Fibrocapsa japonica* (Fig. 1) and *Heterosigma akashiwo* (Fig. 3) have been observed in Dutch and French waters several times [1, 2, 3]. Although these species were reported to cause harmful effects to mariculture in Japanese [4] and French waters [7], there have been no such reports for other European waters so far. This note reports on results of routine sampling programmes in Dutch and in particular German coastal waters and focusses on *F. japonica* and in lesser detail on *H. akashiwo*.

Fibrocapsa japonica**Field observations**

In the summer of 1997, the species was found in almost all samples from the Dutch Algal Bloom Programme. In preserved samples, cell counts showed densities of up to 2 cells/cm³.

In Germany, *F. japonica* has been observed near Sylt (pers. comm. M. Elbrächter, Biologische Anstalt Helgo-

Method	Avg. Cells counted in 3 cm ³	SD	CV (%)
LM	262	14	5.34 (n=5)
FCM	240	10	3.99 (n=5)

Tab. 1 Comparison of light microscopy (LM) and flow cytometry (FCM) counts of cultured *F. japonica*

land). During a survey in the German Bight in July 1995 (RV Heincke), the species was observed alive on board, but not counted due to low densities. Also, since that summer, *F. japonica* has been found in phytoplankton samples from the Wadden Sea near the harbour of Büsum, on the west coast of Schleswig-Holstein [5, Fig. 2]. In 1996 and 1997, *F. japonica* was also listed in the messages of the German "Algenfrühwarnsystem" (AlgFES, Algae Early Warning System) for the German Wadden Sea [6].

At Büsum harbour, phytoplankton samples are taken weekly. At this location, *F. japonica* concentrations increased from maximum numbers of 28 cells/cm³ in 1995 and 30 cells/cm³ in

1996 to 115 cells/cm³ in 1997 (counts by light microscopy in Lugol preserved samples). During the summer of 1997, *F. japonica* cells were also counted by flow cytometry (FacsVantage Cell Sorter, Becton Dickinson). Dotplots of the samples show a distinct group with very high red fluorescence and light scatter signals (Fig. 2). This cluster was positively identified as *F. japonica* by sorting the cells onto microscopic slides and subsequent light-microscopic examination. *F. japonica* was first detected in the flow cytometric samples mid-July, at an already high concentration (107 cells/cm³). The highest cell concentration of 327 cells/cm³ was recorded on July 24. After this date, concentrations decreased to about 5 cells/cm³.

In response to the bloom situation at Büsum Harbour at the end of July, a grid survey was carried out in Meldorf Bay off Büsum on July 31 (RV Südfall). Concentrations of *F. japonica* were very variable between stations, with peak numbers again near Büsum Harbour (Station 5, 128 cells/cm³), and decreased dramatically towards the inner bay stations, and also offshore (Fig. 2).

Cultivating, counting and toxin identification

F. japonica from Büsum harbour was isolated and brought into culture in 1995 (FTZ culture collection). With this material, a comparison between light microscopic (LM) and flow cytometric (FCM) countings was performed to confirm the flow cytometry data. *F. japonica* undergoes a dramatical change when preservative is added: the cells clump together and usually cannot be counted reliably for calibration. We solved this problem by using a combined preservative (Formaldehyde, methanol free,

Fig. 1 *Fibrocapsa japonica*: Glutaraldehyde fixed, and live specimen (inset). Note the dramatic morphological change following fixation.

Fig. 2. Flow cytometric dotplot (forward light scatter vs. chlorophyll fluorescence), of a sample from Büsum Harbour (July 24, 1997). *F. japonica* is represented by the uppermost cluster.

10%, 1 cm³ / 60 cm³ fluid and Lugol (one drop of a Lugol solution, 100 g KI and 50 g KI₂ / 1 dm³ with 100 cm³ Acetic acid 96%). Counts were made using 3 cm³ culture material (5 replicates). The counts for LM were made using this preserved material, FCM counts were made using live material (Table 1). A t-test showed no significant differences between the two counting methods (1% significance level).

We strongly advise our preservation method for microscopic counting *F. japonica* cells.

From these unspecific cultures, toxic compounds were analyzed at the Terramare Institute at Wilhelmshaven. A new toxin was identified. This compound is structurally related to brevetoxin in being a cyclic polyether, and also contains a lactone moiety. However, it is more polar, and carries free OH-groups. Preliminary tests indicate that this toxin interferes with signal transfer from nerve to muscle, presumably involving ion channels. The mode of action appears to be different from brevetoxin. In the mouse- diaphragm-test fibrocapsin

shows higher activity than brevetoxin at the same concentration. The animal-test pointed out that fibrocapsin has a toxicity near tetrodotoxin. The detection limit of the toxin appeared to be at approximately 225 cells/cm³ (with a toxicity test using luminescent bacteria). This threshold level was exceeded at Büsum Harbour during three observations in July 1997, but the water body rich in *F. japonica* was apparently diluted before higher, hazardous concentrations could emerge.

Conclusions

Concentrations of this potentially harmful flagellate along German coasts have reached higher levels than previously reported for this region. It appears that *F. japonica* has become more wide-spread in coastal areas of the North Sea. Under favourable conditions, i.e. warm and sunny weather, and a stable water column, it could well form harmful blooms in the coastal North Sea, as reported for Japanese waters.

Heterosigma akashiwo

Near the Dutch coast, the potentially toxic raphidophyte *Heterosigma akashiwo* (syn. *Heterosigma carterae*) was found for the first time in an algal bloom near Noordwijk on August 4, 1994, with cell numbers approx. 2.400 cells/ cm³ [2]. In German waters, this species was observed in Büsum Harbour and Friedrichskoog in samples in the summer of 1997. Cell concentrations of this species are difficult to count, as in preserved samples the cells deteriorate very soon and therefore cannot be identified easily. However, several cells were observed and identified in living samples.

Video recordings of *H. akashiwo* from the French coast showed a very high resemblance to the specimens found in the Dutch North Sea in 1994 and German Wadden Sea in 1997.

Due to the uncertainties in identifying *H. akashiwo* in preserved samples it is often overlooked in preserved material. Therefore, this species cannot be taken into account in biomonitoring programmes, in which only preserved samples are analysed. However, its presence has been demonstrated in the waters of the Netherlands and Germany.

Acknowledgments

Video tapes of *H. akashiwo* from the harbour of Camaret sur Mer in France (used for comparing Dutch and German video-images) were made by Werner Dietrich from Büsum (October 1997).

We like to thank Gerd Liebezeit and Michaela Nannen from Forschungszentrum Terramare at Wilhelmshaven and Hans Bigalke, Medizinische Hochschule, Hannover, for information on the toxins of *F. japonica*.

Fig. 3 *Heterosigma akashiwo* (sample Friedrichskoog).

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♦ Toxicology

Okadaic acid and carcinogenesis

Okadaic acid (OA) is one of the main toxins involved in Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (DSP), a human seafood intoxication. This phenomenon of high morbidity covers a large geographical area and its expansion induces important problems for shellfish aquaculture and industries. In some countries, monitoring programs have been developed and the shellfish commercialisation is restricted and allowed only below definite levels of toxin content. However, DSP chronic exposure has been suggested to induce digestive tract tumor formation. It is also noteworthy that DSP occurs in several countries such as Japan, Chile, Norway, Holland and Spain, which are known to have high incidences of stomach cancer (Fujiki et al., 1987). In order to understand the possible implication of OA in carcinogenesis, it is important to study its effects at the different stages of cancer formation.

Carcinogenesis is a process consisting in three stages: initiation, promotion and progression. i) The initiation stage, irreversible, induces genetic damage to DNA. ii) Promotion is a reversible process. During this stage, the initiated cells are stimulated by tumor promoters, leading to a selective growth. iii) Progression is an irreversible phenomenon: the cells are more and more aggressive and present increasing genetic abnormalities.

Genotoxicity, mutagenicity

Negative results were obtained when testing the mutagenicity of OA by the Ames test in *Salmonella typhimurium* TA100 and TA98 with or without a microsomal metabolic activation system. A similar negative result was also obtained with two other inhibitors of protein phosphatases 1 and 2A, microcystin LR and nodularin. Moreover, no any initiation activity of OA was shown in experiments conducted on BALB/3T3 cells. Thereby, these tests have not brought any evidence to support the genotoxic activity of OA. However, other results suggest that OA does have a genotoxic capacity: increase of mutation frequencies for some locus and induction of sister chromatid exchange in presence of bromodesoxyuridine.

In order to bring further data regarding the genotoxicity of OA, its capacity to form DNA adducts has been studied. An adduct is the product formed by the covalent binding of an electrophilic chemical compound to a nucleophilic site of cellular macromolecules such as proteins or DNA. The formation of DNA adducts is a necessary but not a sufficient step in chemical carcinogenesis. However, the data obtained to date provide unequivocal evidence that many, if not most, adducts have the potential to cause mutations either during DNA replication at the damaged site or

during error-prone DNA repair. The ³²P post-labelling (Reddy & Randerath, 1986) is one of the techniques available to detect DNA adducts formation. This method presents a high sensitivity and can be used without prior knowledge of the adduct structures. Recent studies using this technique have shown that low doses of OA can produce DNA adducts during exposure of different cell types cultures or even zebrafish embryos (Fessard et al., 1996; Huynh et al., 1997). The way by which OA induces those adducts still remains unknown. Did it bind directly to DNA bases or is it via the formation of electrophilic metabolites? Did OA enhance the formation of a covalent binding between endogenous molecule(s) and DNA? These are subjects of further research to better understand the genotoxic capacity of OA.

It is worth noting that other toxins are also considered genotoxic. For example, nodularin, a PP1 and 2A inhibitor, has been found to have an initiating activity, this toxin being 400 times more potent than diethylnitrosamine. Moreover, some compounds, such as the ochratoxin A mycotoxin, providing negative results with mutagenicity tests, like the Ames or the Mutatox tests, have been finally classified as genotoxic for their ability to induce DNA adduct formation and have been proved to be involved in cancer outbreaks.

Tumor promotion

In 1987, Fujiki et al. have shown that an application of OA on mouse skin induces irritation and induction of ornithine decarboxylase activity, suggesting that this toxin can be a tumor promoter. In 1988, Suganuma et al. demonstrated this potentiality during a two stage carcinogenesis experiment in rodent. OA appeared to be a tumor promoter as potent as TPA for inducing papillomas and carcinomas. In 1992, experiments conducted on rats with OA added to drinking water after an initiation treatment with NMNG demonstrated that OA is also a tumor promoter for glandular stomach. This result points out that OA differs from tumor promoters like TPA or teleocidone not only by its action pathway but also by the target organs. Finally, Yuasa et al. (1994) have shown that OA and its class of compounds administered orally can induce cell proliferation in the rodent gastrointestinal mucosa (oesophagus, stomach, guts) as well as in skin.

Two stage carcinogenesis experiments with rodents have demonstrated that others protein phosphatases inhibitors are also potent tumor promoters: DTX-1 in skin and glandular stomach, calyculin A on mouse skin, microcystin LR and nodularin on rat liver.

Controversial results were obtained with similar two stage carcinogenesis experiments conducted in a cell system: some authors have described a promoter effect while others were not able to detect transformation. Moreover, OA has been shown to inhibit cell transformation induced by other agents.

Oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes

Inhibition of PP1 and 2A caused by OA type compounds leads to induction of oncogenes and inactivation of tumor suppressor gene proteins. Both effects are correlated with tumor promotion and essentially with proliferation of initiated cells.

Oncogenes

Expression of several oncogenes, such as c-abl, c-fos, c-jun, jun B, jun D, is induced by OA in different cell types. The c-fos and c-jun mRNA accumulation is not only due to a transcription increase but also to the mRNAs stabilisation. Like TPA, OA induces c-jun protein

phosphorylation which seems to stimulate its transcriptional activity. However, while the TPA induction of oncogenes is quick and temporary, the effect of OA is slower but lasts for a longer time or is biphasic.

Tumor suppressor genes

OA induces the phosphorylation of pRb and p53 proteins. It can also inhibit the dephosphorylation of p53. The phosphorylation of pRb decreases its binding to cellular oncoproteins and induces activation of the transcription factor E2F. The hyperphosphorylated p53 cannot form tetrameres and this disrupts the expression of down-regulating cell growth genes. This event can lead to the conversion of cells acquiring a transformed phenotype enhancing cell growth.

Apoptosis

Numerous toxic agents induce apoptosis (i.e. programmed cell death), specially in proliferating cells. This phenomenon can be important in carcinogenesis by retarding tumor growth, which is suggested to result from an imbalance between proliferation and apoptosis.

Specific modifications of apoptosis seem to be induced in cells treated by OA. However, if an internucleosomal DNA fragmentation typical of apoptosis can be obtained, it highly depends on the OA dose. At the same time, it has been shown that OA inhibits apoptosis induced by others compounds. In this case, it has been suggested that OA can inhibit the dephosphorylation of some proteins essential for apoptosis.

Gap junctions

Inhibition of gap junctions has been proposed as a mechanism by which initiated cells can isolate from surrounding normal cells and their regulation growth influences. A loss of these junctions can then play an important role in the carcinogenetic process, a lot of tumor promoters, like TPA, inducing a decrease of these intercellular communications (Budunova & Williams, 1994). However, no gap junctions inhibition has been observed in different cell types treated with OA, except for doses inducing morphological changes. Moreover, the gap junctions constituent protein, connexine 43, is not modified by OA, while its phosphorylation is induced by TPA.

Recent studies have pointed out that

OA type tumor promoters, as well as TPA type tumor promoters, provoke in fact an induction of the Tumor Necrosis Factor α (TNF- $\mu\alpha$) and it looks like that the tumor promotion capacity of this type of toxins, protein phosphatases 1 and 2A inhibitors, can act via this endogenous promoter (Fujiki & Suganuma, 1994). Then, it can be suggested that OA can be considered as a genotoxic compound forming (directly or indirectly) DNA adducts and that its promotion capacity is in fact due to the TNF- $\mu\alpha$ induction. In that case, we must be aware that the risks incurred for human health, mainly during chronic intoxications, are under-estimated. Therefore, the toxins levels allowed for consumption should be reconsidered.

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◆ International

Saxitoxin regulations

The Organisation for the Prohibition of Chemical Weapons (OPCW) which is based in The Hague, Netherlands, is responsible for implementing the Chemical Weapons Convention (CWC). The Convention *inter alia* strictly controls the manufacture and use, as well as the transfers and re-use, worldwide of certain treaty-regulated ("Scheduled") chemicals. Saxitoxin is one such chemical, and it is included under Schedule 1. Chemicals under that Schedule may only be transferred between States Parties (to the CWC) and once transferred, cannot be re-transferred to a third country. Furthermore, the OPCW must be given at least 30 days notice prior to any such transfer. All this is without reference to a minimum amount which might escape these regulations.

The issue presented before the OPCW is the unintended consequence resulting from a strict application of these rules to, *inter alia*, the use of saxitoxin as a reference standard in test procedures for paralytic shellfish poisoning

(PSP), including in relation to diagnostic test kits. The OPCW Secretariat is presently collecting information in order to assist the Organisation in making an educated and sensible decision on this issue. Towards this end, we would be very interested in receiving more information along the lines of the questions outlined below.

- 1) What are the advantages of diagnostic kits containing saxitoxin *vis-à-vis* other test methods, and how wide spread is their use today. What is your expectation in relation to the future demand for test kits containing the toxin as a reference standard.
- 2) Do you know of any companies which manufacture, and trade, in test/diagnostic kits for PSP poisoning containing saxitoxin; and also companies which purify and/or export saxitoxin itself for PSP monitoring or other (e.g. neuro-pharmacological research) purposes.
- 3) Have the (OPCW) regulations hindered, or even prevented, adequate and timely supplies of saxitoxin reaching those who requested it? If so, what were the consequences? More specifically, is this an issue from the supply perspective?
- 4) What are the ongoing research activities which require regular supplies of saxitoxin and have there

been delays in getting timely supplies. If so what suggestions do you have for redressing this hurdle?

- 5) What would happen *vis-à-vis* research if the supply is reduced?
- 6) And finally, any names and contact details of those working on similar issues.

These are some of the issues which we feel need to be addressed further. Not only would we appreciate your thoughts on the above, but also your views on any other issue you feel we may have omitted or which may arise in the future.

We would be grateful for any advice and suggestions you can give us. Thank you in advance for your kind assistance. We are of course available for any questions you may have and look forward to hearing from you.

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◆ Ireland

Re-occurrence of Winter Toxicity

In HAN issue No 14 (page 2) we reported on the detection of toxicity of unknown aetiology in mussels from Killary Harbour, on the west coast of Ireland. The toxicity persisted from November 1995 until June 1996. At the time, no known toxins were detected in the shellfish and no known toxic phytoplankton species were identified in water samples. Mice injected with acetone extracts of mussel hepatopancreas gave a "PSP like" response with respiratory difficulties, spasms, paralysis and death within 20 – 90 minutes. Subsequent analysis has revealed the presence of at least one previously unknown toxin (Yasumoto 1997), which has been tentatively named spiramino acid. The toxin is known to cause marked necroses of parenchymal cells in peripheral portions of lobuli in the pancreas, focal necroses

in the liver and/or swelling of hepatocytes when administered either orally or by interperitoneal injection to mice (Ito et al, 1997). Consumers of contaminated mussels suffered severe diarrhoea, nausea and vomiting.

In November 1997 we received reports of illness (severe vomiting and diarrhoea) in consumers of mussels from the Arranmore Island region of Donegal, northwest Ireland. Again no known toxic phytoplankton species were present in water samples examined microscopically and mouse bioassays gave identical reactions to those described above, with death times ranging from 35 – 60 minutes. PSP bioassays were negative and analyses carried out by Dr. Marisa Fernandez at the European Union (EU) Reference Laboratory on Marine Biotoxins (EU-RLMB) in Vigo, Spain showed that

Okadaic acid, DTX1, DTX2, and their acyl derivatives, were undetectable. The clear similarities to the toxic event in Killary Harbour in 1995 suggested that the present toxicity was due to the re-occurrence of spiramino acid. This was confirmed by analysis of a sample of mussels by prof. Yasumoto in Sendai Japan Harvesting of shellfish from the affected area is currently prohibited.

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◆ New Zealand

Sea lion mass mortalities

A serious mass mortality event is currently sweeping through the two main breeding colonies of the New Zealand (Hooker's) sea lion (*Phocarctos hookeri*), with 30-40% of this year's pups already dead, and indications of increasing mortalities amongst adult females.

The New Zealand sea lion is found only in New Zealand waters and is one of the world's rarest seal species. In 1997, based on pup production estimates, the population was estimated at between 11,000 and 15,000 animals. Once distributed throughout New Zealand, from the tip of the North Island to Campbell Island, deep in the subantarctic, the species was taken to the brink of extinction by commercial sealers of the early nineteenth century. The major concern in recent times has been the impact of accidental catches in the trawl fishery for squid around the Auckland Islands, which is one of New Zealand's most important deepwater fisheries. For each of the past four years Ministers of Conservation and Fisheries have set a catch limit for sea lions. The squid fishery was closed early last year, because the sea lion catch limit was exceeded.

Over the past ten years, the Department of Conservation (DOC) has been monitoring the main breeding colonies of Dundas and Enderby Island, part of the Auckland Islands group located

some 420km south of New Zealand's South Island. These two colonies (which collectively occupy an area roughly the size of six football pitches) account for some 95% of the sea lion breeding population. Annual pup production in recent years has been approximately 2,500 animals. Dundas Island is responsible for 80% of all pup production, but is surrounded by rocky reefs and is much harder to access than Enderby, where DOC has a research station.

DOC scientists arrived at Enderby Island in mid-January, and everything seemed to be normal. However, when weather conditions permitted a visit to Dundas on 26 January, the team discovered some 700 recently-dead pups. Symptoms included puffy eyes, ulcerated anuses and vaginas and lesions on the head. Dying pups often showed spasms and paralysis. Fewer adults than usual were on the beach, but at that time there were no signs that the older animals had been affected. Returning to Enderby, the team soon found that pups were beginning to die there also. In addition, adult females started showing signs of paralysis. Afflicted animals also had small raised lesions on the belly and neck. Post-mortems have shown pus-filled swellings around the salivary gland in the neck. The most recent estimate on the day of this posting is that 111 pups

have died on Enderby, and a further 150 are unaccounted for. 20% of the adult females on the breeding beach are dead or afflicted with lesions or paralysis. The numbers of adult females on the beach are considerably lower than normal. An unknown number of females (and males) may have died at sea, and some pups are consequently starving to death.

Samples from autopsied pups and females and six pup carcasses were flown back to the mainland by helicopter on 29 January. Pathologists from Massey University Cetacean Investigation Centre in Palmerston North will begin detailed examinations of the samples on Monday 1 February.

Further updates will be posted with MARMAM (<http://is.dal.ca/~whitelab/marmam.htm>) on a weekly basis.

Any helpful advice or assistance will be warmly welcomed.

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◆ South Pacific

First regional HAB initiative

On 14 November 1997 a workshop on potentially harmful microalgae in the South Pacific was held as a specific session at the Conference on Marine Benthic Habitats & Their Living Resources, Noumea, New Caledonia. The conference addressed marine monitoring and management and its application to Pacific island countries. The conference was co-sponsored by the IOC and the South Pacific Applied Geoscience Commission (SOPAC). It was organized by the Moss Landing Marine Laboratories (US) and IFREMER (France).

The purpose of the session on harmful microalgae was to present an over-

view of the knowledge on the topic in the South Pacific region and, in general, the methods that can be employed to monitor and curtail the impacts of harmful algae on the human population. The session was chaired by Dr. Jorge Diogène (IOC) and Dr. Anne-Marie Legrand and Dr. Yasuwo Fukuyo acted as co-chairs.

The session had participants from Australia, Canada, Commonwealth of the Northern Marianas (CNMI), Cook Islands, Fiji, France (New Caledonia, French Polynesia, Metropolitan area), Guam, Hong Kong, Japan, Kenya, Kiribati, Marshall Islands, Mexico, New

Zealand, Niue, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Spain, Taiwan, Tonga, Tuvalu, United Kingdom, USA (including Hawaii) and Vanuatu.

The potential risk of ciguatera in relation to the presence of *Gambierdiscus toxicus* was discussed. In particular the question of the relationship between ecosystem disturbance (coral reefs) and densities of *G. toxicus* were raised. The effects of anthropogenic alteration of the benthic habitat (ship wrecks) or natural causes (hurricanes, recent volcano formation) in relation to the occurrence of harmful algae were discussed. Other issues such as fluctuations of toxicity, tox-

in detection methods, and the relationship between *G. toxicus* densities and other organisms (sea cucumbers) were addressed.

The question was raised on whether ciguatera is the main problem regarding harmful marine microalgae in the South Pacific region, and/or if other syndromes should be considered. It was suggested that the real importance of ciguatera had to be defined in order to consider it a priority. Some epidemiological data on ciguatera cases in the South Pacific are available from the South Pacific Commission. These data were presented, and demonstrated the importance of ciguatera in the region.

Attendants were invited to contact the IOC, the IOC Science and Communication Centres (Dr. Diogene), and the IOC/WESTPAC-HAB (Dr. Fukuyo) for information, teaching material, and sup-

port. Attendants were also invited to contact their governments and encourage them to strengthen their collaboration with the IOC on this issue.

The workshop concluded by recognizing the importance of problems caused by microalgae in the South Pacific, and noted with concern the absence of coordination among scientists in the region.

It was recommended to list scientists, managers and institutions already implicated on harmful algae research and/or management and those potentially interested in the subject; to strengthen distribution of information on harmful microalgae to scientists, managers and institutions and stimulate their participation in training activities, research projects and working groups related with harmful algae; to gather experts (scientists, managers) from the South Pacific and pro-

mote discussion on harmful algae issues in the region; to invite other institutions, regional entities and countries in the South Pacific to joint efforts with IOC and cooperate in the development of the HAB Programme in the region.

The IOC is coordinating the actions to take and invites all interested to collaborate to fulfill the recommendations. Those interested please contact J. Diogene at the IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Instituto Español de Oceanografía, Centro Oceanográfico de Vigo, Cabo Estay – Canido, APTDO. 1552, 36080 Vigo, Spain; fax: +34 86 – 49 23 51; e-mail: VIGOHAB@VI.IEO.ES, or the IOC Harmful Algal Bloom programme. IOC Secretariat, 1 rue Miollis, 75732 Paris cedex 15, France ; fax: + 33 1 45 68 58 12; e-mail: hab.ioc@unesco.org

◆ ICES

Small-scale physics and harmful algae

A theme session titled 'The Role of Small-scale Physical and Biological Processes in the Dynamics of Harmful Algal Blooms', was organized by P.Gentien and P.Donaghay at the Annual ICES Science Conference in Baltimore, 25 September – 3 October 1997.

Physical-biological interactions at small-scale have been identified as key processes in the understanding of HABs. This statement became obvious during the session due to development and application of new instrumentation, some of which was presented during the session, such as particle-size analyzers, syringe samplers, fast nutrient profilers and optical sensors.

Thin layers located in the pycnocline are sometimes subject to erratic movements and appear to be hydrodynamically confined. Mesoscale advection of these layers, which is still poorly understood, would allow a time-scaling of the populations of concern.

Conceptual models by which these thin-layers may be produced by shear have been presented. However, it appears that, at present, these models are not sufficient to fit the observations and, in particular, their duration and geographical extent. Chlorophyll concentrations observed can result from interca-

tions of cell behaviour with physics, which lead the algae to concentrate in zones where growth is enhanced and/or mortality rates considerably reduced.

Different species may coexist in different layers on the same profile, being associated with specific environments, such as huge blooms of *Pseudonitzschia* in the bottom boundary layer.

Some experimental work has shown that the coordinates of the ecological space refer to the intensity of small-scale turbulence and predator concentration, dinoflagellates being clustered generally at low turbulence intensity. However, further experimental work demonstrates the large range of variation of the effect of turbulence on the growth rates of dinoflagellates: some are stimulated at high energy. Furthermore, it appears that the effects on cells depend on the time of exposure and the energy. Turbulence may also induce excess mortality in chain forming diatoms. So, generally, low turbulence can favour dinoflagellates versus diatoms, when considering biomass production models. However, when species-specific population dynamics are considered, it is necessary to determine the response of this species to small-scale turbulence.

It has been established that the coef-

ficient of turbulent energy dissipation ($\hat{\alpha}$) does not really give much information about the immediate cell environment. A new technique, the holographic camera, allows 3D measurements of flow at the pertinent scale (10 μm). In the near future, this technique should permit direct measurements of turbulent strain on cells both in the lab and in the field and relate them to the turbulent energy dissipation coefficient.

An important challenge will be to relate processes operating at the scale of a cell to the effects on the population and its distribution in time and space.

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The local organizing committee.

◆ Philippines

International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety

The Second International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS) was successfully held on 17-21 November 1997 at Sarabia Manor Hotel in Iloilo City, Philippines. It was hosted by the University of Philippines, Marine Science Institute and the College of Home Economics at Diliman, and the Institute of Aquaculture and the Division of Biological Sciences of the University of the Philippines in the Visayas at Iloilo. The Conference was chaired by Rhodora V. Azanza of the Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines who is also Vice-chair of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms, and the Coordinator of the ASEAN Canada Red Tide Network. Supporting agencies included the Department of Science and Technology (through its Philippine Council for Aquatic and Marine Research and Development and National Research Council of the Philippines), Agriculture (represented by its line-agency Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources) and Health of the Philippines and private agencies such as the Southeast Asian Fisheries Development Center and EASYCOM (Iloilo's first Internet service provider). The IOC provided financial support to participants coming from four developing countries.

The first ICMSS was held in Sydney, Australia on 13-17 November 1994. The

second ICMSS provided a forum for scientists from many different disciplines, growers, and regulators. Discussions focused on the latest research, commercial practices and standards concerning the contamination, purification and overall safety of bivalves with respect to chemical, biological and microbiological contaminants. The Conference emphasized the problems and safety of shellfish in Asia.

This meeting was attended by more than 80 participants from 18 countries. The Philippines, Australia, Japan, New Zealand, Canada, the United Kingdom, China, Taiwan, the United States, Vietnam, Poland, Denmark, Indonesia, France, Mexico, the Netherlands and Spain; 37 papers and 1 video were presented, 17 of which were from Asia, 8 were from Europe, 7 were from US-Canada, 4 were from Australia-New Zealand, and 1 was from Latin America. These papers were classified into 9 sessions/groupings, namely: (1) Biology/Ecology of molluscan shellfish, (2) Microbiological/Biological contamination, (3) Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP): Causative organisms, (4) PSP: Toxicity and detection, (5) Toxic Algal Contaminants, (6) Biotxin monitoring, (7) Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) monitoring and management, (8) Shellfish safety, and (9) Management and regulation.

Simultaneous workshop sessions were held on the following subjects; i) molluscan shellfish safety: Problems and needs in developing countries; ii) Enhancement of Private Sector/Industry participation in molluscan shellfish safety programs; and iii) Molluscan shellfish safety: Research and development priority areas.

Papers presented during the Conference that will pass editorial requirements will be published in a special issue of the *Journal of Shellfish Research*.

In the local press ('Today', p.9, Dec. 9/97 issue), the call 'to speed up passage of shellfish code' for the Philippine government and lawmakers was highlighted. Both Drs. Rhodora Azanza and Sandra Shumway have emphasized the need for a concerted effort between government, the private sector and shellfish farmers to come up with a comprehensive shellfish sanitation code, during their interviews with the press.

Recommendations were made on specific actions to address problems and needs in developing countries. It was recommended to develop a directory of scientists and experts in all aspects of molluscan shellfish safety, to develop a mechanism for exchange of information concerning molluscan shellfish safety (inter-net and/or printed), and to develop a molluscan shellfish safety manual that establishes regionally harmonized rules and regulations compatible or consistent with international standards.

The need for enhancement of private sector/industry participation in molluscan shellfish safety programme was stressed. Given limited resources, it was recommended that education programmes should be directed first to the industry and then to the general public. Access to information through networking e.g. the IOC newsletter, etc. (Internet is not thought to be best route because industry may not be "wired" in everywhere).

The working session also debated research priority areas. One area that requires attention is the mitigation and treatment of the effects of harmful organisms. Regarding harmful algae, several actions were presented in relation to mitigation strategies. It was stressed that the discussion regarding their possible application should be extremely careful and the environmental impact should be of major concern. It was suggested to be better to learn to "accommodate" nature rather than alter it, especially in marine waters where water movement and transfer cannot be controlled. No large-

scale introduction of any species or substance should be attempted until the consequences are well known. Examples of mitigation techniques were i) use of clay, with concern on the effect of sedimentation on benthos and eutrophication, ii) alteration of phytoplankton assemblages, iii) introduction of parasites (e.g. to alleviate *Alexandrium* sp.) with concern for the specificity that has to be clearly defined.

Several other issues related to applied and fundamental research were raised. It was proposed that the effectiveness (UV)/ineffectiveness (ozone) of meth-

ods for treatment for PSP toxins in depuration plants should be clarified. The need for more studies on the movement, bio-transformation and bio-degradation of marine toxins through the food web was expressed. Such studies could provide a better understanding the effects of toxins on target organisms, binding and mechanisms of action of toxins and the possible role of detoxifying enzymes. Stress was put on the development of treatments and antidotes. It was stressed that good scientific data are necessary to establish regulations regarding shellfish safety.

An extended report including recommendations obtained in the workshops is located at the web site <http://www.unesco.org/ioc/oslr/hab.htm> and is also available upon request to the IOC (jorge.diogene@vi.ieo.es, hab.ioc@unesco.org, rhod@msi01.cs.upd.edu.ph)

The Third ICMSS will be chaired by Dr. Sandra Shumway of the Southampton College, Long Island University, New York, USA in the year 2000.

Dinoflagellates on cd-rom

Multimedia dinoflagellate identification

Dinoflagellates, distributed world-wide, are an important component of sea- and freshwater systems and are thought to be potential progenitors of toxins responsible for seafood poisoning. Identification of dinoflagellates is difficult and time-consuming. At present access to species information and identification is limited because the literature is scattered in a vast number of sources. However, electronic information systems, such as Linnaeus II, can provide computer-guided identification of these organisms.

Linnaeus II software was created by the Expert Center for Taxonomic Identification, ETI, of which UNESCO is a partner. This group is dedicated to improving the quantity, quality and accessibility of taxonomic information via interactive multimedia software on a global scale. In developing Linnaeus II, ETI has addressed the taxonomic need for a universal tool to create interactive identification keys, to document biodiversity, to enter and store species information in text and graphic format, and to

easily exchange standardized datasets among specialists. Thus this information system can promote worldwide accessibility of species data via the electronic highway [1].

Dino-Linnaeus is a multi functional database containing species information on dinoflagellates from around the world, from the Caribbean Sea, to the SW Indian Ocean and to the North Pacific Ocean. This data file was compiled using Linnaeus II, a multimedia computer program that allows the specialist to enter, store and access species information, and to develop and use interactive identification keys on their own computer. Data can be stored in text, picture and video (movie) files.

At present access to dinoflagellate data is confined, but in using Linnaeus II we intend to develop taxonomic monographies and regional geographical data resources that ETI will compile and release on CD-ROM. Now interactive, multimedia taxonomic species information can be accessed easily and inexpensively, making this program an excellent modern teaching tool [1] for the identification of marine dinoflagellates.

Linnaeus II

This software is a modern interactive research tool created by and for taxonomists and biodiversity researchers. Linnaeus II is a user-friendly program that can be used on a Macintosh or Windows PC. Data entry is simple using pull-down menus, keyboard commands and/or clicking on buttons. This program has three main components: A) **Taxonomic**

Fig. 1. From the Navigator the user can access other sections of Dino-Linnaeus via clicking on the icons in the left field. A brief introduction to Linnaeus II is in the right field.

Databases, B) Identification Key, and C) Geographical Information System (GIS). All sections are fully multimedia and accessible via the Navigator (Fig. 1).

Taxonomic databases

This section of Linnaeus II is made up of three main databases: *Species Cards* – designed to store species descriptions, taxonomic data and literature references in text format, along with pictures and movies; *Higher Taxa* – section designated to enter multimedia information on phyla, order, class, etc.; and *Species List* – section listing all species and higher taxa names entered into Dino-Linnaeus.

The *Species Cards* are made up of five data fields: a) *Description*, b) *Taxonomy*, c) *Synonyms*, d) *Literature*, and e) *Media Clips*. All fields in the *Species Cards* allow for unlimited data entry.

- Description* field contains the taxonomic description of the species in text form. The information in this field can be viewed in two modes, *Detail* and *Overview*. In *Detail* mode a large view screen allows access to the other information fields in the card, whereas in *Overview* mode a general picture of the species appears on the right with species description on the left, and no access to the other fields in the card (Fig. 2). The *Description* field is divided into user-defined sections for the specific group to retain uniformity in data entry.
- Taxonomy* field stores the most current taxonomic hierarchy for that particular species (phyla, class, order etc.). The taxa are also all linked to the *Higher Taxa* database; i.e. clicking on a name brings up the respective higher taxa description card.
- Synonyms* field stores all known synonyms and common names with author(s) and dates.
- Literature* field lists all relevant citations of the species cited in the *Species Card*. Citations are first entered into the *References* database with keywords/species names and then copied to the *Species Card* literature field. This linking eliminates entering repetitive citations.
- Media Clips* field stores all pictures, movies and sounds relating to the species. The first clip listed should be a general illustration of the species since this is the picture that will display in *Overview* mode

Fig. 2. Overview mode where a general picture of the species is displayed, here *Prorocentrum hoffmannianum*.

in the *Description* field. An unlimited number of pictures and movies can be added following the designated format.

Higher Taxa cards are identical to the data fields found in the *Species Cards*, but without an *Overview* mode. Either card can be accessed indirectly via the *Species List*: clicking on a particular species or taxa name brings up the desired card.

The taxonomic databases also include three supporting databases: *Introduction*, *Glossary* and *References*. The *Introduction* database was designed to store general information on the taxonomic group or specific methodology. In Dino-Linnaeus the *Introduction* section contains three topics: >What is a Dinoflagellate?<, >Identifying Dinoflagellates<, and >Harmful Dinoflagellate Blooms<.

The *Glossary* database stores the definitions and illustrations for all scientific and technical terms (with synonyms). Most definitions in Dino-Linnaeus are taken from *Identifying Diatoms and Dinoflagellates* [2]. The *References* database contains all dinoflagellate literature cited in the program. The user can easily search through the *Glossary* and *References* sections through keyword fields. Moreover, all sections/databases in Linnaeus II are linked through the automatic hyperlinks, so cross-referencing

is simple: clicking on an unknown word prompts a search in the *Glossary* section for the term.

Identification key: identifyit

IdentifyIt is a matrix-based key that allows multiple entry of characters and states to facilitate identification and diagnosis of an object (higher taxa or species). This section of Dino-Linnaeus is made up of structured databases of character states that can be linked to short text (A), long text (T), illustrations (P) and movies (M) to help define them.

IdentifyIt is a fast and effective system for species identification. The user can use any and all characters known about the specimen, even if it is damaged or incomplete. Any number of character states (even >unknown<) can be chosen, and based on the selections, the program sorts the object list, by percentage hits, and determines the probability of each object to best fit the character set. To verify the results of the computerized key the user can click on the object name with the highest percentage points and view the respective *Higher Taxa* or *Species Card*. The user can also compare a number of species with common character states by clicking on the *Compare* button [1]. *Identify-It* files in Dino-Linnaeus include toxic and non-toxic tropical benthic dinoflagellates.

Geographical information system: mapIt

MapIt is a grid-based geographical distribution system designed to store biodiversity data at regional or global levels. With this system the specialist can enter, study and compare distribution patterns of one species or more, view overlay distributions and biodiversity ranges of different species for a particular area of the world. *MapIt* would provide geographical distribution maps of dinoflagellates in the newer version of Linnaeus II.

Dino-linnaeus networks/-eti partners

In using Linnaeus II we are committed to continue developing Dino-Linnaeus for data storage and identification of marine dinoflagellates. Such multimedia databases can cultivate and simplify world-wide cooperation and interaction among specialists to exchange scientific data. We are currently establishing regional and international dinoflagellate networks to continue building the Dino-Linnaeus database with different projects; e.g. tropical planktonic dinoflagellates, neritic athecate toxic dinoflagel-

lates, etc. Dino-Linnaeus is a large undertaking that requires the expertise of many experienced taxonomists. All interested scientists should contact ETI to establish participation in the Linnaeus II program (e-mail: info@eti.bio.uva.nl). As ETI Partners members receive a free copy of the Linnaeus II software package. To ensure format and data entry uniformity contributors should send their data files to R.A. Gulledge or M.A. Faust for incorporation into Dino-Linnaeus. The networks then collaborate to compile modern species information and identification data sets. The completed data files are reviewed by two outside reviewers. And finally the completed systems are sent to ETI and are released on CD-ROMs which are free to the authors and available at cost to others. With ETI's FTP site (file transfer protocol) working on a project with international researchers has been simplified: storage and retrieval of data files is possible at the PC terminal [3].

Completing such a project would produce a highly useful and much needed computerized system to access dinoflagellate species data, to study dinoflagellate biodiversity, and monitor changes in species occurrence in the marine environment.

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2. K.A. Steidinger and K. Tangen, in: *Identifying Diatoms and Dinoflagellates*, C.R. Tomas, ed. (Academic Press, Inc., New York), pp. 387-584 (1996).
3. K.W. Estep, G. Gijswijt, M. Brugman and F. MacIntyre, *The Linnaeus II Manual: Version 1.1 for Windows*, 73 pp. (1996).

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The Fourth WESTPAC Scientific Symposium

The Fourth IOC – Western Pacific Subcommission (WESTPAC) International Scientific Symposium was hosted by the Ocean Research Institute of the University of Tokyo, the University of Ryukyus and the Ministry of Education, Science, Sports and Culture of Japan from February 2-7, 1998. The venue of the said Symposium was the Convention Center in Okinawa. "The Role of Ocean Sciences for Sustainable Development" served as the theme of the Symposium. There were 5 keynote speakers with talks concentrating on the achievements and plans of the Global Oceanographic Observing System (GOOS) program and the Northeast Atlantic GOOS project, the geology of Western Pacific Region and the coastal living resources of WESTPAC.

C. Summerhayes (Director of GOOS), in his keynote address entitled: "Implementing GOOS, the Global Ocean Observing System", said that the project is moving rapidly from planning into implementation through (i) pilot

projects, (ii) technology demonstrator projects, (iii) incorporation or adaptation of existing national or international operational oceanographic systems, and (iv) development of purpose built systems. He also mentioned that scientists involved in the GOOS project plan to negotiate with the IOC HAB programme for possible collaboration as they will be doing with other existing programs involved in oceanographic/marine studies.

The different fields of study in oceanography such as Physics, Geology, Chemistry and Biology were covered by the oral and poster contributions from about 200 participants from the WESTPAC region and the rest of the world. Contributions on Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in the region were the following:

- (1) "Harmful algal bloom management programs in Southeast Asia" by R. V. Azanza which is based on her review/visit of the member countries of the ASEAN region, in her

capacity as the Coordinator of the ASEAN-Canada Red Tide Network in May, 1997. This paper presented a review of harmful algal bloom programs in Southeast Asia, especially those in line with the regional red tide/HAB alert and information networks. Likewise, the needs and concerns for improved monitoring, research and management of HABs for the region were highlighted in this paper;

- (2) "Temporal and spatial distribution of sand-dwelling dinoflagellates in a tidal flat of Yashima Bay, the Seto Inland Sea, Japan" by S. Montani and L. Huang which is based on a 1-year quantitative study of benthic dinoflagellates in a tidal flat of the cited study area. Results of this study suggested that while temperature seems to play the most important role in the succession of these sand-dwelling dinoflagellates, nutrition status may be the deciding factor in their vertical distribution;

- (3) "The establishment of a red tide monitoring center in Samar, Philippines" by J. T. Racuyal, R. C. Dioc-ton and R. T. Severo, Jr. discussed the need to have more red tide monitoring centers scattered within the Philippine archipelago so that the government can have quick access to relevant information about red tide situations. Such data/knowledge can serve as basis by managers to draw up contingencies and minimize the effects of harmful algal blooms on fisheries and public health; and
- (4) "Role of waves in initiating and triggering algal blooms" by R. P. Babaran and R. A. Espinosa espoused the idea that waves (generated by wind stress) may actually play a key role in the onset of algal blooms – a hypothesis which is not new in the field.

Dr. Yasuwo Fukuyo, chairman of the IOC WESTPAC Harmful Algal Bloom

project reported on the achievements of the project which was primarily the training of monitoring and research personnel and the dissemination of reference materials for Southeast Asia, some of which were in collaboration with the ASEAN-Canada Red Tide Project.

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◆ Gulf of Mexico

New HAB experimental facility

New research activities are developing at the US Environmental Protection Agency's Environmental Research Laboratory, Gulf Ecology Division, in Gulf Breeze, Florida. With a commitment to assisting the national effort to resolve the increasing ecological, economic, and public health problems associated with harmful algal blooms (HABs), the Laboratory has recently established a new multi-disciplinary HAB research team composed of scientists with a variety of expertise that will be applied to this issue. We are in the process on developing a HAB Experimental Culture and Exposure Facility that will be the focal point for our studies on HAB nutrient ecophysiology, toxin production, diagnostic indicators, and effects of toxin exposures on aquatic organisms. We anticipate that the facility will be operational in early 1998.

We have recently incorporated a HAB page on the Gulf of Mexico Aquatic Mortality Response Network (GMNET), which you can visit at, <http://pelican.gmpo.gov/gmnet/gmhome.html> (follow the Items of Interest link to HABs). Our goal is to expand

the GMNET aquatic mortality reporting activities to include information on HAB events in the five Gulf coast states. We think this database will be invaluable for examining causal relationships between aquatic mortalities and HABs, and we would like to hear about other existing or planned efforts. I would like to take this opportunity to invite all Gulf of Mexico colleagues to get involved with the new GMNET activities. Over the next several weeks, I will be contacting as many of you as I can to discuss our goals and their implementation. You would like to be added to the GMNET listserver or want more information on this or our other HAB activities, you can contact me at:

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◆ HAB ART

Algal sculptures

If you happen to be passing through Hiroshima, plan to visit Dr. Haruyoshi Takayama at the Hiroshima Fisheries Experimental Station for a rare treat indeed. Many of you may be familiar with Dr. Takayama's taxonomic papers and SEM's of dinoflagellates but few, we suspect, know of his other talent—carving.

Dr. Takayama began carving replicas of phytoplankton 12 years ago. His first object was a Raphidophyte, *Chattonella antiqua*, and the collection now numbers about 32 species and 35 pieces. The dinoflagellates are carved from pine, cherry, and other woods and all are done to scale. We are told that his wife scolds him regularly to not scatter scraps and thus he does some of his carvings during cruise time. The collection is kept at the laboratory in a small museum.

The 'organisms' are excellent teaching tools and make explanation of morphological characteristics a simple task, even for beginners. He uses these carvings during his training course on identification of red-tide organisms. It must be a real treat for his students when during his discussions of plates, apical pores, and other things seemingly foreign, he produces these models for examination. Exquisite only begins to describe them.

If you would like to see these sculptures on display at the 9th International Conference on Harmful Algae in Tasmania, contact Dr. Takayama and encourage him to bring them along!

Dr. Haruyoshi Takayama, Hiroshima Fisheries Experimental Station, Ondocho, Aki-gun, Hiroshima 737-12 Japan, Fax: 81 823 52 2683.

Sandra Shumway

Future events

6th Canadian Workshop on Harmful Marine Algae, St. Andrews, NB, Canada, May 27-29 1998. Topics of the workshop include; ecology and oceanography of harmful algal events, management and socioeconomic impacts of toxic and toxicological and epidemiological studies, models, and toxins. Contact: Jennifer Martin, Biological Station, St. Andrews NB Canada EOG 2X0; Phone: +506-529 5921; Fax: +506-529 5862; e-mail: martinjl@mar.dfo-mpo.gc.ca

IOC-Germany Training Course on Qualitative and Quantitative Determination of Algal Toxins, Friedrich-Schiller-University of Jena, Germany, 6-16 October 1998. The objective of the course is to improve the participants expertise on qualitative and quantitative determination of algal toxins in order to enable them to make reliable determination of algal toxins from phytoplankton species causative of harmful algal events. The course will contain a theoretical, and a practical part on toxin chemistry and toxicology. The practical part of the course consists of different analytical methods for determination of PSP, DSP, ASP, TTX as well as blue-green toxins. Priority will be given to younger scientists. Lectures at the course will include: Dr. Bernd Lucas and colleagues from Friedrich-Schiller-University of Jena, Dr. Malte Elbrächter, Biologische Anstalt Helgoland and a guest lecturer. Application forms can be obtained from the Harmful Algal Bloom Programme Office, IOC, 1, rue Miollis, 75732 Paris Cedex 15, France, fax: +33 1 45 68 58 12, e-mail: hab.ioc@unesco.org. Deadline for applications is 1 July 1998.

9TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HARMFUL ALGAL BLOOMS, 7-11 February 2000, Tasmania, Australia. The conference will provide a broad forum for phycologists, microbiologists, toxicologists, physiologists, molecular biologists, aquatic ecologists and managers to address and exchange research findings and perspectives concerning all aspects of toxic and harmful

algae, including freshwater cyanobacteria and ciguatera (fish poisoning). Harmful algae and their toxins pose a growing global problem for human health, aquaculture, fisheries, seafood trade, tourism and the aquatic environment at a time when human reliance on coastal zones for food, recreation and commerce is expanding. Contributions are invited which address the following topics: * Taxonomy of harmful algae, using conventional as well as sophisticated molecular and immunological approaches * Population dynamics of harmful algal blooms, including coupling of physical and biological processes, and interactions with zooplankton, viruses and bacteria * Ecophysiological, chemical and pharmacological aspects of algal toxins, with a focus on new analytical methods and novel toxins or toxic episodes * Monitoring and management of harmful algal blooms as they relate to eutrophication, aquaculture, public health and shipping (ballast water problem). Options for prevention, control and mitigation will be especially emphasized. Contact: HAB 2000 Conference Secretariat, Conference Design Pty Ltd, PO Box 342, Sandy Bay Tasmania 7006, AUSTRALIA, Tel: +61 3 62243773, Fax: +61 3 62 243774, E-mail: mail @cdesign.com.au, or: Gustaaf M. Hallegraef, School of Plant Science, University of Tasmania, GPO Box 252-55, Hobart, Tasmania 7001, AUSTRALIA, Tel: +61 3 62 262623, Fax: +61-3-62 262698, E-mail: Hallegraef@utas.edu.au (Gustaaf Hallegraef), Web Page: http://www.utas.edu.au/docs/plant_science/P.S._Homepage.html.

For a more comprehensive overview of up-coming activities and events you should visit the IOC International Marine Meeting List at the IOC homepage at <http://www.unesco.org/ioc/infserv/meets.htm>. The list of meetings related to the International Year of the Ocean might also be of interest <http://www.unesco.org/ioc/iyo/conferences.htm>

Literature for developing country libraries

Limited copies of the following titles are available from the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Denmark (see address below), to libraries of marine science institutions in developing countries only:

- The Genus *Alexandrium* Halim (Dinoflagellata). E. Balech, 1994.
- Algae. An Introduction to Phycology. C. van den Hoek et al., 1995.
- Identifying Marine Phytoplankton. C. Thomas et al. (eds.), 1997.
- Proceedings of the International Symposium on Ciguatera and Marine Natural Products, Hawaii, 8-10 August 1994. Hokama et al. (eds.) 1995.
- Proceedings of the First International Congress on Toxic Cyanobacteria, Denmark, 20-24 August 1995, and, Proceedings of the First Maj and Tor Nessling Foundation Symposium on 'Recent developments in Cyanobacterial Research', Finland 16-18 August 1995. Moestrup et al. (eds.) Phycologia, Vol. 35 No. 6, 1996.
- Photography through the microscope. Kodak. J.G. Dally, 1997.

Applications must be submitted and signed by the responsible librarian, and should indicate why the requested title is of specific interest to your institution and its ongoing research or teaching. No requests from individuals will be honoured.

IOC publications

- Summary Report of the Fourth Session of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms, Vigo 30 June - 2 July 1997. Available in English, French, Spanish.
- Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP), Volume 1, IOC *Manuals and Guides*, No. 31.

These publications are free of charge and available from the IOC Secretariat.

1, Rue Miollis, 75732 Paris, Cedex 15 France, Fax: +33 1456858, e-mail: hab.ioc@unesco.org

- Manual on Harmful Marine Microalgae, IOC Manual and Guides No. 33.
- Harmful and Toxic Algal Blooms. Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Toxic Phytoplankton, Sendai, Japan, 12-16 July 1995.

The Manual and the Sendai Proceedings are free of charge but a fee of US\$ 30 will be charged for handling. A cheque issued for the IOC SCCHA, University of Copenhagen (see address below), should accompany all orders. Only prepaid orders will be accepted. Excepted from the handling fee are marine science libraries and scientists in developing countries which can apply for delivery free of charge.

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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